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● *Araneus elongatus* Yin, Wang & Xie, 1989 is a junior synonym of *Perilla teres* Thorell, 1895 (Araneae: Araneidae)

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Abstract: The spider species formerly recorded from China as *Araneus elongatus* Yin, Wang & Xie, 1989 is transferred to the genus *Perilla* and synonymized with *Perilla teres* Thorell, 1895. This taxonomic revision is based on the examination of newly collected specimen from Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region, which are consistent with the original description of *A. elongatus* from Yunnan Province. We provide a detailed redescription of the species (as *P. teres*) based on the newly collected material, accompanied by high-definition color images of its diagnostic morphological features. A global distribution map of *P. teres* is presented, incorporating the confirmed records from China. The specimen studied is deposited in the Animal Specimen Museum of the College of Life Sciences, Jinggangshan University (ASM-JGSU).

Keywords: Guangxi, junior synonym, *Perilla teres*, taxonomy

● 长腹园蛛是圆柱佩勒蛛的次定同物异名（蜘蛛目：园蛛科）

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摘要: 本文将先前在中国记录为长腹园蛛 *Araneus elongatus* Yin, Wang & Xie, 1989 的蜘蛛物种, 转移至佩勒蛛属 *Perilla*, 并将其归为圆柱佩勒蛛 *Perilla teres* Thorell, 1895 的同物异名。此项分类学修订基于对来自广西壮族自治区新采集标本的检视, 这头标本与来自云南省的 *A. elongatus* 原始描述相符。我们基于新采集标本对该物种 (即 *P. teres*) 进行了详细的重新描述, 并提供了鉴别形态特征的高清彩色图像。文中给出了 *P. teres* 的全球分布图, 其中包含了来自中国的确认记录。研究标本存放于井冈山大学生命科学学院动物标本馆 (ASM-JGSU)。

关键词: 广西, 同物异名, 圆柱佩勒蛛, 分类学

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● Introduction

The Araneidae family is one of the most speciose groups within the order Araneae, with over 198 genera and 3,160 species recorded globally (World Spider Catalog 2025). As one of the most speciose genera in the family, *Araneus* Clerck, 1757 has long served as a taxonomic “dumping ground”, resulting in a particularly poor and confused state of its taxonomy (Mi *et al.* 2024). The spider *Araneus elongatus* was described from Yunnan Province, China, over three decades ago (Yin *et al.* 1989). Since its original description, this species has received little taxonomic attention, and its generic placement as well as its relationship to other regional species have remained uncertain.

Morphological observations suggest a close resemblance between *A. elongatus* and *Perilla teres* Thorell, 1895, a species historically recorded from Southeast Asia (Thorell 1895; Simon 1909; Kuntner 2002). Based on newly collected specimen from Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region, China, which align with the concept of *A. elongatus*, we perform a detailed morphological analysis. By comparing this new material with the original description of *A. elongatus* and the diagnostic characters of *P. teres*, we are able to directly assess their conspecificity.

Based on similarities in general morphology and copulatory organs, we formally propose that *Araneus elongatus* be considered a junior synonym of *Perilla teres*. To support this revision and enrich the characterization of this species, we provide a comprehensive redescription of *P. teres* based on the newly collected specimen, accompanied by high-definition photographs and an updated global distribution map.

● Material and methods

Specimen was examined using a Jiangnan SZ6100 stereomicroscope with a KUY NICE CCD camera. Female copulatory organ was dissected and examined in 80–85% ethanol. The epigyne was cleaned with pancreatin. The specimen was photographed with an Olympus CX43 compound microscope with a KUY NICE CCD camera.

Somatic morphological measurement was taken with the AxioVision software (SE64 Rel. 4.8.3) and given in millimetres. The body length of the specimen excludes the chelicerae and spinnerets. Terminology of the female genitalia follows Kuntner *et al.* (2008).

Leg measurements are given as total length (femur, patella, tibia, metatarsus, tarsus). The abbreviations used in the figures and text are: **ALE**, anterior lateral eye; **AME**, anterior median eye; **At**, atrium; **CD**, copulatory duct; **CO**, copulatory opening; **PLE**, posterior lateral eye; **PME**, posterior median eye; **Spe**, spermatheca; **ESc** – epigynal scape; **Spe** – spermathecae.

● Taxonomy

Family Araneidae Clerck, 1757

Genus *Perilla* Thorell, 1895

Perilla teres Thorell, 1895

Figs 1–2, 3D

Perilla teres Thorell, 1895: 196 (♂♀, holotype not examined); Kuntner 2002: 283, figs 1–9 (♂♀); Kuntner *et al.* 2008: 173, fig. 14A–H (♂♀); Kuntner *et al.* 2009: 1453, fig. 2C (♀).

Perilla cylindrogaster Simon, 1909e: 110 (♀).

Araneus elongatus Yin *et al.*, 1989: 331, figs 5–9 (♀, holotype not examined); Yin *et al.* 1997d: 137, fig. 52a–e (♀); Song *et al.* 1999: 238, figs 137L–N, 147O (♀). **syn. nov.**

Material examined: 1 ♀ (ASM-JGSU-Ara-5923), CHINA, Guangxi Zhuang Autonomous Region, Chongzuo City, Ningming County, Chengzhong Town, Butterfly Valley, 22°12′50.389″N, 107°03′21.658″E, 29 August 2025, Hao-Chong Wan leg.

FIGURE 1. *Perilla teres* Thorell, 1895, female: **A** Habitus, dorsal view **B** Same, ventral view **C** Same, lateral view **D** Cephalothorax, dorsal view **E** Same, ventral view **F** Same, lateral view. Scale bars: 1.0 mm (A–C), 0.5 mm (C–E).

Diagnosis. See Kuntner (2002) for diagnosis.

Description. Habitus as in Figs 1A, B, 3D. Total length 6.49, carapace (Fig. 1A, C, D, F), orange to brown, oval-shaped, 2.28 long, 1.74 wide, longer than wide, fovea longitudinal, radial furrows distinct. Cephalic region low. Eyes sizes and interdistances: AME 0.13, ALE 0.09, PME 0.09, PLE 0.12; AME–AME 0.09, AME–ALE 0.15, PME–PME 0.04, PME–PLE 0.22, AME–PME 0.04, AME–PLE 0.23, ALE–ALE 0.66, PLE–PLE 0.73, ALE–PLE 0.04. MOA 0.28 long, front width 0.34, back width 0.22. Chelicerae reddish-brown, relatively short and robust in the basal part, with 4 promarginal and 3 retromarginal teeth. Endites dark brown, square, with a row of setae on inner margin. Labium dark brown to black, trapezoid. Sternum brown to black, shield-shaped, with several setae, anterior margin almost straight, lateral margin slightly sharp, longer than wide. Legs (Fig. 1) yellow to black, with dark brown annulations and dense short setae, first femur strong and sigmoidal in dorsal view; measurements: I 7.21 (2.27, 0.79, 1.72, 1.66, 0.77); II 4.83 (1.41, 0.63, 1.20, 1.01, 0.58); III 2.51 (0.77, 0.51, 0.53, 0.36, 0.34); IV 4.30 (1.26, 0.65, 1.38, 0.65, 0.36). Abdomen (Fig. 1A, B) yellowish to gray, columnar, very long, with four pairs of yellowish-brown spots on dorsal view, 4.21 long, 1.57 wide; caudal part protrudes considerably beyond spinnerets,

pedicel to spinnerets 1.72 long, post-spinneret region 1.80 long. Spinnerets situated approximately midway on the ventral view of the abdomen.

Epigyne (Fig. 2A–D). Scape thick, pad-like, slightly protrudes beyond the epigyne. Atrium small, arc-shaped, located at the posterior margin of the epigyne, slightly sclerotized. Copulatory openings small, situated on each side of the atrium. Copulatory ducts short, curving towards the vulval margin before connecting directly to the spermathecae. Spermathecae elongate and moderately spaced, with an inter-spermathecal distance to spermathecal width ratio of approximately 3:4.

Distribution. China (Guangxi, this study; Yunnan, Yin *et al.* 1989), Myanmar (Thorell 1895), Vietnam (Simon 1909), Malaysia (Kuntner 2002) (Fig. 4).

FIGURE 2. *Perilla teres* Thorell, 1895, female: **A** Epigynum, ventral view **B** Vulva, ventral view **C** Same, ventral view **D** Same, lateral view. Abbreviations: At – atrium, CO – copulatory opening, CD – copulatory duct, ES – epigynal scape, Spe – spermathecae. Scale bars: 0.1 mm.

FIGURE 3. A–C Habitat of *Perilla teres* Thorell, 1895, showing the sampling point **D** Living specimen of *Perilla teres* Thorell, 1895, female.

FIGURE 4. Records of *Perilla teres* Thorell, 1895 in Asia.

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● Additional information

Author contributions: Conceptualization: X Li & H-C Wan. Project administration: K-K Liu. Resources: H-C Wan. Visualization: X Li. Writing—original draft X Li & J Luo, Writing—review and editing: X Li & K-K Liu.

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中华大刀螳 *Tenodera sinensis* Saussure, 1871
Chengkou County [城口县], Chongqing
photograph by Zi-Hao ZHU [朱梓豪]